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Hyaluronic acid-functionalized CaCO₃ crystals as novel polyelectrolyte multilayer reservoirs for CPT-RB (Chemotherapy and Photodynamic therapy) targeting multiple myeloma

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Abstract:

The properties of calcium carbonate (CaCO₃) make it a suitable option for drug delivery, particularly for medicinal substances with short half-lives, poor stability, limited solubility, and poor bioavailability, as well as restricted distribution or penetration. A significant step in CaCO₃ fabrication is the production of polyelectrolyte multilayered capsules. Isolated soyasaponin-integrated CaCO₃ crystals were functionalized with (chitosan/polyacrylic acid) and (polydopamine/hyaluronic acid) as multilayers. Rose Bengal as photodynamic therapy and camptothecin as chemotherapy were integrated during fabrication separately and simultaneously. Characterization of CaCO₃ crystals was investigated by using SEM, TEM, FTIR, XRD, and zeta potential measurements. Results showed an assembled structure of CaCO₃ crystals with strong integration of Rose

Bengal and Camptothecin. Polyelectrolyte multilayered capsules obtained by CaCO₃ removal were observed to have cellular uptake in multiple myeloma cell lines. Hyaluronic acid-functionalized capsules were investigated in fibroblast normal cell lines under confocal microscopy to detect their application as targeted therapy for multiple myeloma. The flow cytometry and confocal microscopy confirmed ROS generation in both irradiated and non-irradiated multiple myeloma cell lines. It concluded that polyelectrolyte multilayered capsules are a good reservoir for encapsulating both chemotherapy and photodynamic therapy molecules simultaneously, and this could increase the potential therapeutic application.

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Keywords: Calcium carbonate Poor bioavailability Polyelectrolyte Multilayered Capsules

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